

GABRIEL ISLAND - ÎLOT GABRIEL

ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH,

FIELDWORK SEASONS 2022

MACH – Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage

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ARCHAEOLOGICAL RESEARCH ON GABRIEL ISLAND

A new season of archaeological research was conducted in Mauritius in 2022, as part of the Mauritian Archaeology and Cultural Heritage (MACH) project, based at Stanford University, US, and the ISLand Project (MSCA_GA No 897004, Project ISLand), funded by the European Commission. The team, led by Dr. Cianciosi under the supervision of Prof. Seetah, surveyed Gabriel Island for the first time.

The ISLand Project focuses on the quarantine system established in the Indian Ocean, with a case study in Mauritius. Flat Island, one of the sites preliminarily surveyed by the MACH team since 2014, became the main object of analysis. Through detailed surveys of the island, which was established as a quarantine station in the middle of the nineteenth century, we identified several preserved structures associated with a quarantine camp, two hospitals, a cemetery, and other living quarters and facilities.

In collaboration with AGTF and the Forestry Service (formerly the National Parks and Conservation Services (NPCS) of Mauritius), another objective of our research was to assess the feasibility of this island as a heritage attraction. If viable, we aimed to provide evidence on how visitor activities could be sustainably managed. The archaeological research was conducted under the project 'Documentation and Conservation of the former quarantine station in Flat Island, Mauritius'.

During this campaign, we focused on Gabriel Island, the small sister islet close to Flat Island, which was only occasionally used as a quarantine station. In particular, it served as the main quarantine station in 1856, when two vessels from India, namely the *Hydaree* and the *Futtay Mombarrack*, arrived in Mauritius with cases of cholera onboard. They were ordered to place their passengers, mostly indentured labourers, in quarantine. At the time, construction was underway on Flat Island, as a result, forcing the ships to land on nearby Gabriel Island. However, the islet lacked adequate facilities for all immigrants. There were insufficient shelters, and the water shortage worsened due to a cyclone, preventing regular water provisions from reaching the island. Furthermore, the doctors and the officials in charge lacked experience and organization

skills. Between January 14 and May 6, the harsh conditions, aggravated by the cholera epidemic, resulted in the deaths of nearly half of the 692 immigrants who landed on Gabriel Island (Report 1857). The indication of a burial ground on Thomas Corby's map (1857) could be the location of the cemetery area used during those tragic months (fig. 1). After the catastrophic event, significant investments were made to build permanent infrastructure on Flat Island and organize a proper team of officials responsible for managing the health institution. However, over the decades of its use, the quarantine station on Flat Island never gained a good reputation, and the complaints from immigrants were numerous. Between the 1860s and the 1920s Gabriel Island was used for temporary shelters and specific supporting functions for the main station on Flat Island.

The 2022 fieldwork season, extended between November 23rd and 28th, included a preliminary survey of the entire islet, documentation of the preserved structures and archaeological features, and the excavation of test pits in the supposed burial ground used in 1856.

Fig. 1 Map drawn by T. Corby (1857) with the detail of the Burial Ground on Gabriel Island.

THE CAMP

Gabriel Island, situated windward of Flat Island, is impacted by both tide and wind effects. Its shorelines are characterized by coralline sands and basalt boulder fields. Coralline sand deposits particularly cover the western half and southern rim of the island. Along the windward north-eastern perimeter, basalt dominates surface features,

exposed due to coastal geometry and wave action. A calcareous limestone platform extends off the southeastern rim, forming a peninsular bridge with significant tidal pool formations.

At the beginning of our fieldwork, a comprehensive survey of the entire island was conducted with the assistance of members from the Forestry Service Department. We identified the main features and several clusters of scattered artifacts that were visible on the surface. The identification of these features was based on the detailed information from the report on the outbreak of cholera in Mauritius in 1856 and the map by Corby in 1857 (fig. 2).

All identified features were located on the western half of the island below the 10 m contour line and recorded as follows:

-GI_STR 101. A dry-stone rectangular structure, partially visible in the vegetation, oriented SE-NW. Ruined stones cover the southwest corner, and a smaller rectangular structure leans against the south side of STR 101.

-GI_STR 102. Similar to STR 101. It is a dry-stone rectangular structure, partially visible in the vegetation, oriented SE-NW.

Both structures were georeferenced for the visible parts, but proper cleaning is needed to uncover the entire structure. They correspond to two of the three 'stores' indicated on Corby's map (fig. 3).

-GI_CAVE: a supposed cave, located 150 m away on the northeast side of STR 101, with basalt boulders featuring three irregular holes. It could potentially be a cave used for recovering basalt rock, but there were no specific signs of tools for extracting stones and they were caused by the action of the waves (Pike 1873: 208).

-Cluster 1: towards the beach, approximately 80 meters north of the stores, a small cluster of some ceramic and glass objects was found scattered on the surface. Fragments of brick were also found not far from Trench C, along its north side.

-Cluster 2: a second cluster of ceramic, iron, and glass objects was discovered on the western tip of the island, between the main path and the shore. Two small groups of artifacts were found 10 m apart (fig. 4).

A fragment of a porcelain bowl features a Chinese (or Japanese) monogram painted at the bottom, while some glassware fragments appear to be medicinal containers. Four glass samples were selected for archaeometric analysis at Stanford University (Prof. Mudrit Trivedi) (fig. 5).

Fig. 2 Map of Gabriel Island with the archaeological features documented during the survey 2022.

Fig. 3 The stone structures identified as stores.

Fig. 4 The main groups of archaeological finds documented on the surface.

Fig. 5 The bottom of a porcelain bowl (above: inside and outside) and two glass bottle fragments used for medicine (below).

THE BURIAL GROUND

In the report on the cholera outbreak in Mauritius in 1856, Dr. Clerihew, the chief medical officer in Mauritius, advised in a letter to Dr. Finlay, the quarantine doctor: “The greatest care must be taken to prevent any contamination of the atmosphere by the bodies of the dead. Dead bodies ought to be buried at as great a depth as possible, with lime over them, and a larger quantity of lime ought to be placed over the graves of those already buried and covered by a layer of sand or earth. For this purpose, a quantity of lime is sent to you by the Steamer, now despatched [sic!], and if you want more, apply for some to the Contractor at Flat Island, taking care to dip all letters to him in vinegar” (Report 1857:77). A week later, the demoralizing report of the visit Gabriel Island by Dr. Hardie, a member of the government commission, stated: “Graves are to leeward of the camp though not very far from it. The soil is light and sandy. Each man is buried in a separate grave from 5 to 6 feet deep. Has no lime to put over the bodies. Has only two broken spades, now quite worn out, not [sic!] longer in the handles than 4 inches” (Report 1857:97).

Indeed, the map drawn by Corby (fig. 1), the Government Surveyor, in 1857, displays a broad area labeled ‘burial ground’ on the northern side of the island, not far from the stores. We located the burial ground area using GPS and initiated a series of test pits, along a rectangular grid of 120x20 m. The location of the trenches was influenced by the existing vegetation cover. We opted to open areas already cleared to minimize the impact on the vegetation during the excavations.

Fourteen test pits were excavated: six of 1x1 m size (C-H), and eight slightly bigger (A, B, and I-P). The stratigraphy was relatively uniform and homogeneous, consisting of a series of layers of pure sand. Except for the superficial layers, which occasionally contained organic materials, mainly roots, no organic or artificial finds were documented (fig. 6). In each trench we identified at least two stratigraphic units (SU): the topsoil and the geological base. Trenches closer to the seashore documented a sequence of different layers of sand transported and gathered by the wind (fig. 6, C and H). A few trenches were opened in correspondence to a dune, where the sandy layer

under the topsoil was loose and yellowish (fig. 6, A). However, no traces of archaeological layers or finds were recorded, leading us to simplify the sequence into 21 SU.

The trenches were recorded as follows:

Trench	Size	Depth	Evidence/Finds	Note
A	3x2 m	40 cm		SU 1, 2, 3
B	1,5x2 m	70 cm	In SU 1 (topsoil) 1 fragment of white-blue porcelain, in SU 2, below the topsoil, we found a pile of seashells	SU 1, 4
C	1x1 m	130 cm		Profile in the cliff E-W (2 m length), close to the seashore SU 1, 5
D	1x1 m	100 cm	Below the topsoil 3 small animal bones	SU 1, 7, 10
E	1x1 m	70 cm		SU 1, 6
F	1x1 m	100 cm		SU 1, 8, 9, 13
G	1x1 m	100 cm	In the topsoil, 9 small animal bones (shrew?) and 1 bigger animal bone	SU 1, 11, 14
H	1x1 m	140 cm		SU 1, 12
I	1,5x1,5 m	80 cm	In the topsoil 1 fragment of porcelain	SU 1, 15, 17

L	1,5x1,5 m	50 cm		SU 1, 16
M	2x1,5 m	60 cm		SU 1, 18
N	2x2 m	50 cm		SU 1, 19
O	2x2 m	50 cm		SU 1, 20
P	1X1	120 cm		SU 1, 21

Fig. 6 Three trenches (A, C, and H) during the excavation.

THE MEMORIAL MONUMENTS

Following the path along the seashore on the west-southern side of the island, it is easy to reach two monuments on the southern tip, erected by the General Board of Health

of Mauritius in memory of Louis Ernest Bertrand and Horace Lazare Beugeard, who succumbed to smallpox in the 1880s (fig. 7).

The first monument consists of a wooden cross and an epitaph on a tombstone bearing the following inscription:

LOUIS ERNEST
BERTRAND
DIED ON 30TH(?) NOVEMBER 1883
AGED 25 YEARS

We lack additional information about Louis Ernest Bertrand, and it is plausible that he may have served as an assistant to Dr. Beugeard, possibly meeting his demise during his service at the quarantine station.

The second monument, dedicated to Doctor Beugeard, features a quadrangular stone base and an obelisk adorned with a high-relief laurel wreath and a carved inscription:

SACRED
TO
THE MEMORY
OF
HORACE LAZARE
BEAUGEARD
WHO DIED FROM
SMALL POX
CONTRACTED ON THE
THIS ISLAND IN THE PERFORMANCE
OF HIS DUTIES
23RD NOV (partially readable) 1883
AGED 47

On the basement, another inscription says:

THIS MONUMENT IS ERECTED BY THE GENERAL BOARD
OF HEALTH OF MAURITIUS
AS A TESTIMONY OF ITS APPRECIATION
OF THE DEVOTION OF AN ESTEEMED MEDICAL OFFICER

The perimeter of the monument is marked by four cornerstones, resembling small pillars.

Dr. H. Beugeard (born 1836) served as Assistant Surgeon at the civil hospital, in Port Louis in 1864 (De Joux 1865) and passed away on Gabriel Island while attending smallpox patients arriving from the Seychelles (Boodhoo 2020). Another memorial in his honor was erected in the Western Cemetery, Port Louis.

While the monuments serve as memorials, the exact location of their graves remains unknown

Fig. 7 The tombstone in memory of Louis Ernest Bertrand (above) and the monument dedicated to Dr. Beaugeard (below) with details of the inscriptions.

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